

MECHANISMS OF LANGUAGE CHANGE

Samarqand DChTI

Ingliz tili nazariyasi va adabiyoti

kafedrasi katta o‘qituvchisi

N.N. Zubaydova

Annotation: The article deals with significant data about mechanisms of language changes. Moreover, some main examples of types of language change and its importance were discussed.

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Language change is variation over time in a language's features. It is studied in several subfields of linguistics: historical linguistics, sociolinguistics, and evolutionary linguistics. Traditional theories of historical linguistics identify three main types of change: systematic change in the pronunciation of phonemes, or sound change; borrowing, in which features of a language or dialect are altered as a result of influence from another language or dialect; and analogical change, in which the shape or grammatical behavior of a word is altered to more closely resemble that of another word. All living languages are continually undergoing change. Some commentators use derogatory labels such as "corruption" to suggest that language change constitutes a degradation in the quality of a language, especially when the change originates from human error or is a prescriptively discouraged usage[1]. Modern linguistics rejects this concept, since from a scientific point of view such innovations cannot be judged in terms of good or bad. John Lyons notes that "any standard of evaluation applied to

language-change must be based upon a recognition of the various functions a language 'is called upon' to fulfil in the society which uses it". There some causes of changes:

- Economy: Speech communities tend to change their utterances to be as efficient and effective (with as little effort) as possible, while still reaching communicative goals. Purposeful speaking therefore involves a trade-off of costs and benefits.

- The principle of least effort tends to result in phonetic reduction of speech forms. See vowel reduction, cluster reduction, lenition, and elision. After some time a change may become widely accepted (it becomes a regular sound change) and may end up treated as standard. For instance: *going to* ['gou.ɪŋ.tu] → *gonna* ['gɒnə] or ['gʌnə], with examples of both vowel reduction [ʊ] → [ə] and elision [nt] → [n], [ou.ɪ] → [ʌ].

- Expressiveness: Common or overused language tends to lose its emotional or rhetorical intensity over time; therefore, new words and constructions are continuously employed to revive that intensity.

- Analogy: Over time, speech communities unconsciously apply patterns of rules in certain words, sounds, etc. to unrelated other words, sounds, etc.

- Language contact: Words and constructions are borrowed from one language into another.

- Cultural environment: As a culture evolves, new places, situations, and objects inevitably enter its language, whether or not the culture encounters different people.

- Migration/Movement: Speech communities, moving into a region with a new or more complex linguistic situation, will influence, and be

influenced by, language change; they sometimes even end up with entirely new languages, such as pidgins and creoles.

- Imperfect learning: According to one view, children regularly learn the adult forms imperfectly, and the changed forms then turn into a new standard. Alternatively, imperfect learning occurs regularly in one part of society, such as an immigrant group, where the minority language forms a substratum, and the changed forms can ultimately influence majority usage.

- Social prestige: Language may not only change towards features that have more social prestige, but also away from ones with negative prestige, as in the case of the loss of rhoticity in the British Received Pronunciation accent. Such movements can go back and forth[2].

According to Guy Deutscher, the tricky question is "Why are changes not brought up short and stopped in their tracks? At first sight, there seem to be all the reasons in the world why society should never let the changes through." He sees the reason for tolerating change in the fact that we already are used to "synchronic variation", to the extent that we are hardly aware of it. For example, when we hear the word "wicked", we automatically interpret it as either "evil" or "wonderful", depending on whether it is uttered by an elderly lady or a teenager. Deutscher speculates that "[i]n a hundred years' time, when the original meaning of 'wicked' has all but been forgotten, people may wonder how it was ever possible for a word meaning 'evil' to change its sense to 'wonderful' so quickly."

Although independent of grammar, sound changes might well have important consequences for the grammatical system. A good example is the extreme erosion of final consonants in French, which has left singular and plural sounding identical in many cases. While we cannot predict which changes will happen and when, some changes do appear to be more natural than others.

Internally motivated changes of this kind often result in reduced articulatory effort on the part of the speaker. Systemic changes is internally motivated sound changes may have profound consequences for grammar, as the De Gaulle example above illustrated, and in some cases, what the Neogrammarians identified as analogy repairs the damage, by aligning irregular forms with regular ones. Externally motivated changes arise from contact between speakers of different varieties. Normally the contact varieties are closely related, but contact between speakers of mutually incomprehensible languages has also in some cases led to significant structural change. An early study by Gumperz and Wilson showed how regular and prolonged contact between speakers of Kannada, Marathi and Urdu in Kupwar, India, brought about significant convergence between the languages at the syntactic level, even though their lexicons remained distinct. Particular attention has been paid in recent years, however, to exploring the outcomes of contact between speakers of different varieties of the same language. This interest has been fuelled in part by increasing urbanization, which brings together speakers of different varieties in new and unfamiliar settings (the world's officially urban population crossed the 50 per cent threshold for the first time in 2009). In his groundbreaking work *Dialects in Contact*, Peter Trudgill observes that, where contact occurs between speakers of different varieties who are fairly well disposed towards one another, a likely outcome is accommodation, i.e. speakers will unconsciously begin to converge their speech in a variety of ways[3]. The most obvious of these is accent convergence: one notices, for example, that many Britons living and working in the United States begin to replace their intervocalic [t] in words like better, matter with a flapped [r].

Altintas, Can, and Patton (2007) introduce a systematic approach to language change quantification by studying unconsciously used language features in time-separated parallel translations. For this purpose, they use objective style markers

such as vocabulary richness and lengths of words, word stems and suffixes, and employ statistical methods to measure their changes over time. Languages perceived to be "higher status" stabilise or spread at the expense of other languages perceived by their own speakers to be "lower-status". Historical examples are the early Welsh and Lutheran Bible translations, leading to the liturgical languages Welsh and High German thriving today, unlike other Celtic or German variants[4]. For prehistory, Forster and Renfrew (2011) argue that in some cases there is a correlation of language change with intrusive male Y chromosomes but not with female mtDNA. They then speculate that technological innovation (transition from hunting-gathering to agriculture, or from stone to metal tools) or military prowess (as in the abduction of British women by Vikings to Iceland) causes immigration of at least some males, and perceived status change. Then, in mixed-language marriages with these males, prehistoric women would often have chosen to transmit the "higher-status" spouse's language to their children, yielding the language/Y-chromosome correlation seen today.

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